

A Comparative Analysis of the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act 2018, and The United Kingdom Equality Act 2010: Prospects and Challenges

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Abstract:

This paper provides a comparative analysis of disability rights laws in Nigeria and the UK, focusing on Nigeria's Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018, and the UK Equality Act 2010. Using a doctrinal research methodology, the study identifies key differences, finding that the UK Act offers a more robust framework with specific disability definitions, clear accommodation provisions, enforcement mechanisms, and positive action measures. In contrast, Nigeria's Act is broader but less detailed, lacking clear guidelines for enforcement and accommodation. The research recommends revising Nigeria's legislation to adopt a more comprehensive disability definition and expand its scope to better align with international standards.

Keywords: Disability Rights, United Kingdom, Nigeria, Equality Act 2010, Disability Act 2018, Comparative Analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

People living with disabilities face numerous problems and challenges in the contemporary world. With issues ranging from discrimination relating to employment, education, adequate healthcare, and the use of public services. These disabilities also affect their ability to interact with other persons in society socially with the risk of stigma and social exclusion. Recognizing this problem, the Federal Government of Nigeria decided to pass the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act into Law on 21st January, 2018.¹ Before the legislation, the Nigerian Constitution served as the main source of rights for all persons in the Federal Republic of Nigeria. However, its provision is silent on discrimination against people living with disabilities. This makes the Disabilities against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 the primary legislation on issues relating to discrimination against people living with disabilities.

This monumental piece of legislation was designed to fit in with international human rights commitments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948. The legislation marked a turning point in the war against discrimination against people with disabilities and the fight for equal rights for everyone in society. Following its enactment, there is the necessity within the academic realm to dissect this Act. This appraisal is targeted at articulating the objectives of this landmark legislation, stating its key provisions, and analyzing its strengths and weaknesses in promoting equal participation and eradicating discrimination against persons living with disabilities. This appraisal also compares the Nigerian disability with the UK Equality Act 2010 with a view to exploring areas for improvement for the Nigerian Act.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Discrimination involves unfair treatment based on characteristics like race, gender, or disability, leading to exclusion or disadvantage. There are various forms of discrimination. Direct discrimination occurs when someone is treated unfairly due to a trait, such as denying a job to a person with a disability. Indirect discrimination happens when policies, though applied equally, disproportionately affect certain groups, like requiring all employees to work full-time without considering those with disabilities. For example, in *Mojekwu v Mojekwu*² the Court of Appeal Enugu held that the “Oli-ekpe” custom of Nnewi in Anambra State under which male children only inherit their father’s property is unconstitutional because the custom discriminated against female children.

Disability refers to physical, mental, or sensory impairments that limit daily activities, such as mobility issues, blindness, or mental health conditions. Discrimination against

¹ Samuel Ogundipe, “Buhari signs Law banning discrimination against persons with disability” *Premium Times NG* (23 January 2019) <<https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/307474-buhari-signs-law-banning-discrimination-against-persons-with-disability.html?tztc=1>> accessed 6 May 2024.

² [1997] 7 N.W.L.R 283.

individuals with disabilities often involves denying accommodations or limiting access to opportunities, further marginalizing them. Efforts to combat disability discrimination are essential to ensuring equal access to opportunities and full participation in society.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE DISCRIMINATION AGAINST PERSONS LIVING WITH DISABILITIES (PROHIBITION) ACT, 2018

The Act was enacted with a clear set of objectives chiefly aimed at improving the lives of persons living with disabilities in Nigeria which it articulates beautifully and clearly. The act aims to (a) eradicate discrimination against persons with disabilities in Nigeria making it a punishable offense under law;³ (b) raise awareness that will affect the promotion of the rights of people with disabilities while praising their contributions to society;⁴ (c) promote inclusivity of persons with disabilities in all spheres of societal life including religious, cultural, political, and social participation⁵ and (d) protect the rights of persons with disabilities by giving them the same level of participation in societal life.⁶

The Act serves as a comprehensive legal framework aimed at safeguarding the rights and promoting the equal participation of persons living with disabilities in Nigeria. Its objectives also include ensuring the unhindered access of persons living with disability to public spaces,⁷ transportation, and information that might otherwise be inaccessible to them due to their disabilities. Furthermore, the Act empowers persons living with disabilities by granting them the right to free education, at least up to the secondary school level.⁸ Moreover, the Act plays a crucial role in destigmatizing persons with disabilities by mandating the implementation of awareness programs.⁹

In addition to ensuring equal access and opportunities, the Act also addresses the need for reasonable accommodations and accessibility measures in various settings, including workplaces, educational institutions, and public facilities. Overall, the Act represents a significant step towards promoting the rights, dignity, and inclusion of persons with disabilities in Nigeria, paving the way for a more equitable and inclusive society.

³ Section 1, Discrimination against People Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018.

⁴ Ibid, Section 2.

⁵ Ibid, Section 27.

⁶ Ibid, Section 30.

⁷ Ibid, Section 3.

⁸ Ibid, Section 17.

⁹ Ibid, Section 2.

3.1 Challenges in the Nigerian Disabilities Act

While the Discrimination against Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019, is a groundbreaking and commendable piece of legislation, it is essential to acknowledge and address its potential weaknesses and gaps to ensure its effectiveness in protecting the rights of persons with disabilities in Nigeria. One of the primary areas of concern is the enforcement mechanisms outlined in the Act. The Act's efficacy is contingent upon its capacity to impose consequences on those who violate its provisions. There are legitimate questions about whether Nigeria has sufficient resources and capabilities to monitor compliance effectively and address infractions in a timely and consistent manner.¹⁰ Without these resources, the Act's implementation may suffer, and violations could go unaddressed, undermining its intended impact.

Additionally, there is a valid concern about the potential for uneven enforcement across different states, particularly in less developed regions. Nigeria is a vast and diverse country, with significant variations in socioeconomic development and available resources among its states.¹¹ There is a risk that the Act's enforcement may be stronger in more urbanized and developed states, while its impact may be diminished in less developed areas due to resource constraints, lack of awareness, or ingrained societal attitudes towards disability. This challenge underscores the need for a well-coordinated and adequately funded national enforcement strategy, supported by capacity-building initiatives and awareness campaigns at the state and local levels.

Moreover, it is essential to address the broader socio-cultural context and deeply rooted stigma, misconceptions, and negative attitudes towards disability in Nigeria. These societal barriers can hinder the effective implementation and enforcement of the Act. Complementary efforts, such as public awareness campaigns, inclusive education initiatives, and the promotion of positive representation in media and popular culture, can play a crucial role in fostering a more inclusive and understanding society, which can in turn facilitate better compliance with the Act.¹² There is also the problem of education, many persons with disabilities are not aware of the provisions or even the existence of the Act at all. The major persons that the Act addresses do not have access to the Act or sufficient interpretation of it.¹³

The distribution of funds and resources is another flaw. A large financial commitment is necessary for the implementation of accessibility measures, the provision of educational

¹⁰ Arimoro Augustine Edobor, 'Are they not Nigerians? The obligation of the state to end discriminatory practices against persons with disabilities', *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* (2019) 19(2), 89-109.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Edwin Etieyibo, 'Rights of persons with disabilities in Nigeria' *Afrika focus* (2020) 33(1), 59-81.

¹³ Muyiwa Atoyebi, and Prince Igbo, 'An appraisal of the Discrimination of persons living with disabilities(Prohibition Act)' *Omaplex* (6 October 2023) <<https://omaplex.com.ng/an-appraisal-of-the-discrimination-against-persons-with-disabilities-prohibition-act-2019/>> accessed on 7 May 2023.

materials, and the guarantee of healthcare access.¹⁴ The government's commitment to providing sufficient funding to support the Act's implementation is essential to its success. With the Nigerian government operating with a thin budget, there is a high risk of insufficient allocation of funds to the commission.¹⁵

Furthermore, while the Act aims to protect the rights of persons with disabilities and prevent discrimination, it appears to have a narrow focus on specific types of disabilities, such as impairments related to vision, hearing, speech, and cognitive abilities. However, the definition and understanding of disability have evolved over time, and there is a growing recognition that disabilities can manifest in various forms, including physical, sensory, intellectual, mental health, and chronic health conditions.¹⁶ The Act's failure to explicitly acknowledge and address the wide range of disabilities could potentially leave certain groups or individuals with disabilities unprotected or inadequately represented. In summary, while the Discrimination against Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2019, is a significant step forward, its impact will be contingent upon the establishment of robust enforcement mechanisms, adequate resource allocation, capacity-building initiatives, a more accommodating definition of disability, and a concerted effort to address socio-cultural barriers.

3.2 Strengths of the Nigerian Disabilities Act, 2018

The Discrimination against Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 signifies a significant and commendable step by the Nigerian government towards guaranteeing the rights of people living with disabilities and protecting them against discrimination. The Act's broad application is one of its major strengths, as it prohibits discrimination across various domains, including access to public services, employment, healthcare, and education. This comprehensive approach ensures that individuals with disabilities are safeguarded from discrimination not just in one specific setting but throughout their entire lives, fostering an inclusive and equitable society.¹⁷

The Act's provisions regarding employment practices are particularly noteworthy. By mandating that employers make reasonable accommodations for qualified candidates or workers with disabilities, the Act aims to level the playing field and create an environment

¹⁴ Anazonwu Nkemdilim, Paulinus Okah, Ngozi Chukwu, Agha Agha, Anthony Iwuagwu, Chinyere Onalu, Chinwe Nnama-Okechukwu, and Uzoma Okoye, 'Barriers to domestication and implementation of the disability act in southeast Nigeria' *Journal of Social Work in Developing Societies* (2022) 4(1).

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Chineze Sophia Ibekwe, and Onyeka Christiana Aduma, 'The evolution of disability rights in Nigeria: Pitfalls and prospects' *AJLHR* (2019) 3, 137.

¹⁷ Muhammad Mansur Aliyu, 'Rights of Persons Living with Disabilities under the Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act 2018' *IJOCLLEP* (2019) 1, 112.

where individuals with disabilities can thrive and contribute to their fullest potential.¹⁸ This requirement recognizes that disabilities may necessitate certain modifications or adjustments in the workplace, and it places the onus on employers to facilitate these accommodations. Equally, through this Act, reasonable accommodations can take various forms, such as providing assistive technologies, modifying physical infrastructure to ensure accessibility, or offering flexible work arrangements.¹⁹ These accommodations not only enable individuals with disabilities to perform their job duties effectively but also promote their overall well-being and job satisfaction.

Furthermore, the Act's prohibition of discrimination in educational settings is a crucial step towards ensuring equal opportunities for students with disabilities. By barring discrimination in admissions processes, access to facilities, and participation in programs, the Act aims to create an inclusive learning environment where students with disabilities can pursue their academic aspirations without facing unnecessary obstacles or prejudice.²⁰ In addition, any change or adjustment made to a job or work environment that enables a candidate or employee with a disability to participate in the application process or carry out necessary job functions is known as a reasonable accommodation.²¹

Noteworthy, the Act gives the commission the ability to hear complaints about harmful practices, harassment, and discrimination, among other things.²² The creation of these federal commissions is based on the need to have a body to address the problems disabled people face. Additionally, the Act gives accessibility measures a top priority. For people with disabilities, the Act eliminates physical barriers that have historically limited their participation by requiring changes to public buildings and transportation systems. More freedom and mobility are made possible by this accessibility-focused approach.

However, it is important to note that the successful implementation of the Act's provisions will require a concerted effort from various stakeholders, including the government, private sector, educational institutions, and civil society organizations. Adequate resources, infrastructure upgrades, awareness campaigns, and robust monitoring mechanisms will be essential to translate the Act's intentions into tangible outcomes. Additionally, addressing societal attitudes and misconceptions surrounding disability will be a critical component of the Act's long-term impact. In all, the Discrimination against

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Arimoro Augustine Edobor, 'Nigeria's Legislation Against Discrimination of Persons With Disabilities: An Assessment' In *Social, Educational, and Cultural Perspectives of Disabilities in the Global South*, IGI Global (2021) 55-67.

²⁰ Nwamaka Adaorah Iguh, and Maureen Obiageli Ugwu, 'Protecting and Promoting the Rights of Persons with Disability in Nigeria' *IRLJ* (2023) 5, 153.

²¹ Ade Oba Raji, 'What Nigerian law says about treatment of people living with disabilities' *Pulse NG* (28 March 2024) <<https://www.pulse.ng/news/local/nigerian-law-treatment-of-people-with-disabilities/tv116ew>> accessed on 7 May 2024.

²² Section 38, Discrimination against people living with disabilities Act, 2018.

Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 represents a significant milestone in Nigeria's efforts to protect the rights of individuals with disabilities and promote an inclusive society.

4. KEY PROVISIONS OF THE DISCRIMINATION OF PEOPLE LIVING WITH DISABILITIES (PROHIBITION) ACT

The Act represents a paradigm shift in the area of human rights enforcement in Nigeria. Its passage into law illustrates an effort to promote the rights of persons living with disabilities. The measures and provisions in this Act represent an attempt to improve the lives of persons living with disabilities. This section of the research will interrogate the major provisions this Act.

(a) Prohibition of discrimination against persons living with disabilities

This core provision outlaws discrimination against individuals with disabilities in all its forms. It covers various spheres of life, including education, employment, healthcare, access to public services, and even public spaces.²³ The Act generally ensures that individuals with disabilities have equal opportunities and treatment compared to their non-disabled counterparts. It goes further to pronounce discriminations against persons living with disabilities an offense punishable under the law as a misdemeanor; imposing a fine of ₦1,000,000 on corporate bodies and a fine of ₦100,000 naira on an individual or six months imprisonment, or both.²⁴

Discrimination against disabled persons by corporate bodies usually comes in the form of employment or removal from corporate spaces.²⁵ A vivid example is the non-acceptance of wheelchairs in restaurants or the ejection of persons with wheelchairs from restaurants.²⁶ The Act makes employment practices subject to the its scrutiny. Reasonable workplace modifications, like adapted workstations or flexible work arrangements, become mandatory to ensure people with disabilities can perform their jobs effectively.²⁷ In the area of education, schools and institutions are barred from

²³ Rose Adaji and Ibim Dokubo, 'Highlights of the Discrimination against persons with disabilities (Prohibition) Act' Monday NG (14 April 2022) <<https://www.mondaq.com/nigeria/discrimination-disability--sexual-harassment/1183236/highlights-of-discrimination-against-persons-with-disabilities-prohibition-act-2019>> accessed 6 May 2024.

²⁴ Section 1(2), Discrimination against People Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018.

²⁵ Amucheazu Chibike, and Chidebe Mathew Nwankwo, 'Accessibility to infrastructure and disability rights in Nigeria: an analysis of the potential of the discrimination against persons with disability (prohibition) act 2018', *Commonwealth Law Bulletin* (2020) 46(4), 689-710.

²⁶ Chris Johnson, 'Reps summon KFC over discrimination against ex-gov, Gbenga Daniel son' *Daily Post Nigeria* (2 April 2024) <<https://dailypost.ng/2024/04/02/reps-summon-kfc-over-discrimination-against-ex-gov-gbenga-daniels-son/>> accessed on 6 May 2024.

²⁷ Amucheazu Chibike, and Chidebe Mathew Nwankwo, op. cit.

discriminating against students with disabilities. This includes admissions processes, access to facilities, and participation in programmes.²⁸

(b) Establishment of the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities

One of the major provisions of the Act includes the creation of a National Commission for Persons with Disabilities.²⁹ This Commission is to act as the central body for advocating for the rights of people with disabilities in Nigeria and oversee the enforcement of the Act's provisions. Its duties include developing and implementing policies that are to help with the social and educational development and welfare of people living with disabilities.³⁰ The Act also gives the Commission the role of educating and enlightening the public about people living with disabilities to speed up their integration into society. Their work also includes the collection of data and statistics of persons living with disabilities for identification and inclusion in a special national database.³¹

Finally, their function also goes to the private sector where they have the responsibility of working with private companies to make sure that persons with disabilities are taken into consideration when they are making decisions.³² They also receive complaints on violation of the rights of persons living with disabilities and supported the seeking of redress in court, investigation, or sanctioning in appropriate cases.³³ The Commission is also to be headed by a Governing Council which is to conduct the affairs of the commission. The Council is to consist of a part-time chairman, a representative from each of the six geopolitical zones (person living with disability), a representative from the National Human Rights Commission, the National Planning Commission, and representatives from some special federal ministries.³⁴

(c) Accessibility measures for persons living with disabilities

The Act goes beyond prohibiting discrimination. It also mandates the implementation of accessibility measures in public buildings and transportation systems. The Act guarantees the right of a person with a disability to have equal rights to access the physical environment and buildings.³⁵ This includes features like ramps, elevators, tactile paving, and accessible toilets to ensure people with disabilities can access these facilities with ease.³⁶ It supports the remodification of buildings to include access for persons with

²⁸ Section 20, Discrimination against People Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018.

²⁹ Ibid, Section 31.

³⁰ Michael Chukwujindu Ogwezy, 'The Promotion and Protection of Rights of Persons with Disability in Nigeria: An Analysis of the Applicable Theories, Statute and Treaty Laws' *Sri Lanka J. Int'l L.* (2019) 27, 171.

³¹ Ibid.

³² Ibid.

³³ Section 38(a)-(r), Discrimination against People Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018.

³⁴ Ibid, Section 32.

³⁵ Ibid, Section 3.

³⁶ Ibid, Section 4.

disabilities.³⁷ The needs of people with disabilities, especially those who use wheelchairs, should be taken into consideration for all planning approvals. After the legislation went into effect, already-existing public buildings and structures that were previously inaccessible were given five years to make sure that their buildings were accessible moving forward.³⁸ The Act also inputs penalties for violation of these provisions.³⁹ Government and Private Transport service providers also have the responsibility to make provisions for lifts, ramps, and other devices to make accessibility for disabled people easier.⁴⁰ Seaports and Airports in the country are also to follow suit with these provisions.⁴¹

(d) Guarantee of Socio-Economic rights (right to education, employment and healthcare)

The Act makes it a criminal offense to use or employ a person with a disability to beg with a punishment of ₦100,000 or six months imprisonment or both.⁴² The right to education is enshrined in the Discrimination of Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018. The Act guarantees free education for persons with disabilities up to the secondary school level, a crucial step towards dismantling educational disparities.⁴³ This commitment extends beyond financial accessibility. The Act mandates the provision of educational assistive devices, such as specialized software or Braille materials, to cater to the diverse learning needs of individuals with disabilities.⁴⁴ This ensures they can get access and thrive in academic environments.

The right to employment is another critical pillar of socio-economic inclusion. The Act prohibits discrimination against individuals with disabilities in the recruitment, hiring, and promotion processes.⁴⁵ The Act provides for at least 5% of a company workforce to be composed of people with disability.⁴⁶ Employers are obligated to consider reasonable workplace modifications, such as adapted workstations or flexible work arrangements, to ensure people with disabilities can perform their jobs effectively. This fosters a more inclusive work environment and unlocks the potential of a talented and diverse workforce.

³⁷ Ibid, Section 7.

³⁸ Ibid, Section 6.

³⁹ Ibid, Section 8.

⁴⁰ Ibid, Section 10 and 11.

⁴¹ Ibid, Section 12 and 14.

⁴² Ibid, Section 16.

⁴³ Ibid, Section 17(2).

⁴⁴ Ibid, Section 18.

⁴⁵ Ibid, Section 28.

⁴⁶ Ibid, Section 29.

The right to healthcare is fundamental for a life of dignity and well-being. The Act guarantees adequate healthcare for persons with disabilities in all public health institutions without discrimination.⁴⁷ Furthermore, it makes provisions for free healthcare for persons with mental disabilities.⁴⁸ This ensures they have equal access to essential medical services without facing financial constraints. Furthermore, the Act mandates reasonable accommodations, such as sign language interpreters or alternative communication methods, for deaf patients and speech impaired people. This ensures all individuals with disabilities receive the healthcare they deserve.⁴⁹

(e) Educational and awareness program

The Act empowers the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities (NCPWD) and the Ministry of Information to spearhead public awareness campaigns. These campaigns can utilize various media channels, such as television, radio, and social media, to reach a broad audience. Educational messages can focus on dispelling stereotypes and misconceptions surrounding disability⁵⁰. Additionally, campaigns can highlight the rights and capabilities of individuals with disabilities, fostering empathy and understanding within the public sphere.

5. INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES OF THE UNITED KINGDOM (UK) EQUALITY ACT, 2010

The United Kingdom's Equality Act 2010 is a comprehensive piece of legislation that aims to promote equality and prevent discrimination against individuals based on various protected characteristics, including disability. This Act consolidated and streamlined numerous existing laws and regulations, providing a cohesive legal framework for addressing discrimination across various aspects of life, such as employment, education, and the provision of goods and services.⁵¹

The introduction of the Equality Act 2010 was a significant milestone in advancing the rights of individuals with disabilities in the UK. Prior to this Act, disability discrimination was primarily addressed through the Disability Discrimination Act 1995, which aimed to eliminate unequal treatment and promote equal opportunities for disabled individuals.⁵² However, the Equality Act 2010 expanded the scope of protection and introduced new concepts and obligations.

⁴⁷ Ibid, Section 21(1).

⁴⁸ Ibid, Section 21(2).

⁴⁹ Ibid, Section 20.

⁵⁰ Ibid, Section 2.

⁵¹ Bob Hepple, 'The new single equality act in Britain', *The Equal Rights Review* (2010) 5(1), 11-24.

⁵² Ibid.

One of the primary objectives of the Equality Act 2010 concerning disabilities is to ensure that individuals with disabilities are not subjected to unfair treatment or discrimination in various areas of life.⁵³ The Act prohibits direct discrimination, where a person is treated less favorably because of their disability, as well as indirect discrimination, where a seemingly neutral policy or practice disproportionately disadvantages individuals with disabilities. Additionally, the Act imposes a duty on employers, service providers, and public authorities to make reasonable adjustments to accommodate the needs of individuals with disabilities.⁵⁴ Another key objective of the Equality Act 2010 is to promote positive attitudes towards individuals with disabilities and encourage their full participation in society.⁵⁵

Furthermore, the Act establishes the concept of discrimination arising from disability, which occurs when a person is treated unfavorably because of something arising in consequence of their disability.⁵⁶ This provision aims to protect individuals from discrimination based on manifestations or consequences of their disability, such as behavior or appearance. The Equality Act 2010 also introduces the concept of harassment related to disability, which prohibits unwanted conduct that violates a person's dignity or creates an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating, or offensive environment.⁵⁷ Overall, the Equality Act 2010 serves as a comprehensive legal framework for promoting equality and addressing discrimination against individuals with disabilities in the UK.

6. KEY PROVISIONS OF THE UNITED KINGDOM (UK) EQUALITY ACT, 2010

The Equality Act of 2010 of the United Kingdom is a combined legislation that seeks to address and extend prior anti-discrimination laws with the view of offering clear guidelines that enhance equal treatment for all people in the United Kingdom. One of the successful concepts is that the Act fully covers the issues of disability rights, providing equal opportunities and protections for protected people at the workplace, school, and when using services. This section of this research offers a detailed description of the provisions of the Act in the case of disability.

(a) Definition of disability

The Equality Act 2010 is a landmark piece of legislation in the United Kingdom that consolidates and strengthens previous anti-discrimination laws. One of its critical components is the comprehensive definition and protection it offers to individuals with

⁵³ Robin Richardson, 'Equality Priorities and Equality Objectives—the Equality Act 2010, a cautious welcome', *Race Equality Teaching*, (2010) 28(2), 6-11.

⁵⁴ *Ibid*,

⁵⁵ *Ibid*.

⁵⁶ Butlin Sarah Fraser, 'The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities: does the Equality Act 2010 measure up to UK international commitments?', *Industrial Law Journal*, (2011) 40(4), 428-438.

⁵⁷ *Ibid*.

disabilities. Under Section 6 of the Act, disability is defined in a broad and inclusive manner to ensure extensive protection and support for disabled individuals across various domains of life. The Act defines a disability as a physical or mental impairment that has a substantial and long-term adverse effect on a person's ability to carry out normal day-to-day activities.⁵⁸ This definition is purposefully broad to encompass a wide range of conditions, including physical, sensory, cognitive, and mental health impairments.⁵⁹

The term "substantial" is defined as more than minor or trivial, meaning that the impairment significantly impacts the individual's ability to perform basic day-to-day activities.⁶⁰ These activities refer to the fundamental tasks and functions that people typically perform daily, such as dressing, eating, walking, or engaging in social interactions. The impairment must also be long-term, defined as lasting or expected to last at least 12 months or for the rest of the person's life.⁶¹ Temporary conditions that do not meet this duration are not covered under this definition.

Importantly, the Act extends its coverage to progressive conditions. This includes illnesses that are expected to worsen over time, such as multiple sclerosis (MS), HIV, and some forms of cancer. According to Schedule 1, Paragraph 8 of the Act, these conditions are recognized as disabilities from the point of diagnosis, even before they result in substantial adverse effects, ensuring early protection and support. Additionally, the Act covers conditions with fluctuating or recurring effects, such as epilepsy, rheumatoid arthritis, or certain mental health conditions.⁶² The impact of these conditions may vary over time, but they are recognized because they can have significant long-term effects.⁶³ The Act also protects individuals who have had a disability in the past, even if they no longer have the impairment. This provision ensures that individuals who have recovered from conditions like cancer or mental health issues are protected from discrimination based on their medical history.⁶⁴

Certain conditions are explicitly included in the definition of disability. For example, severe disfigurements, blindness, and partially sightedness are automatically covered under the Act.⁶⁵ However, some conditions are explicitly excluded unless they result from an underlying impairment that has a substantial and long-term effect. These excluded

⁵⁸ Section 6(1), Equality Act, 2010.

⁵⁹ Equality and Human Rights Commission, Scottish Human Rights Commission, and Northern Ireland Human Rights Commission. *Progress on disability rights in the United Kingdom*. Equality Commission for Northern Ireland (2018).

⁶⁰ Section 212(1), Equality Act, 2010.

⁶¹ Section 6(1)(b), Equality Act, 2010.

⁶² Equality and Human Rights Commission, *op. cit.*

⁶³ *Ibid.*

⁶⁴ Section 6(4), Equality Act, 2010.

⁶⁵ Schedule 1, Paragraph 3, Equality Act, 2010.

conditions include addiction to non-prescribed drugs or alcohol and certain behavioral conditions like kleptomania or pyromania.⁶⁶

The Equality Act 2010 provides guidance on assessing whether an impairment has a substantial and long-term effect on someone's ability to carry out normal day-to-day activities.⁶⁷ While medical evidence and diagnosis are important, the focus is on the practical impact of the impairment on the individual's life.⁶⁸ Practical examples help determine if an impairment is substantial and long-term. For instance, an individual with a hearing impairment might struggle with listening to a conversation in a noisy environment, or a person with severe depression might find it difficult to get out of bed and engage in regular activities.

Legal protections under the Equality Act 2010 ensure that disabled individuals receive the rights and accommodations they need. In the context of employment, employers are prohibited from discriminating against disabled employees and must make reasonable adjustments to accommodate their needs. These adjustments can include physical changes to the workplace, adjustments to working hours, and providing specialized equipment.⁶⁹

In education, institutions must ensure that disabled students are not disadvantaged. This involves making necessary adjustments to teaching methods, materials, and physical accessibility to support learning and participation.⁷⁰ Service providers, including public and private organizations, must ensure that disabled individuals can access their services. This includes modifying physical spaces, offering alternative communication methods, and training staff to understand and meet the needs of disabled customers.⁷¹ Additionally, according to Section 29, transport providers are required to make reasonable adjustments to ensure disabled people can use public transport, including providing accessible vehicles and clear information.

(b) Discrimination

The Equality Act 2010 provides robust protections against discrimination for individuals with disabilities, aiming to promote fairness and equality across various sectors, including employment, education, and the provision of goods and services. Sections 13-19, 21, and 26 of the Act outline the different forms of discrimination that are prohibited. The Act prohibits several forms of discrimination: direct discrimination, indirect discrimination,

⁶⁶ Schedule 1, Paragraph 5, Equality Act, 2010.

⁶⁷ D Chantal, N Ferreira, A Morris, and D Morris. 'The equality act 2010: five years on', *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law* (2016) 16(2), 61-65.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ Sections 20-21, Equality Act, 2010.

⁷⁰ Section 85, Equality Act, 2010.

⁷¹ Sections 29-30, Equality Act, 2010.

harassment, and victimization. Direct discrimination occurs when an individual is treated less favorably specifically because of their disability.⁷²

Indirect discrimination happens when a policy, practice, or criterion that applies to everyone disproportionately disadvantages individuals with disabilities.⁷³ Unlike direct discrimination, indirect discrimination is often less overt and can arise from seemingly neutral policies. For instance, a company policy requiring all employees to work long hours without breaks may disproportionately affect individuals with chronic illnesses who need regular rest periods. While indirect discrimination can sometimes be justified if the policy is a proportionate means of achieving a legitimate aim, it must be carefully scrutinized to ensure it does not unfairly disadvantage disabled individuals.⁷⁴

Harassment under the Equality Act 2010 is defined as unwanted conduct related to a person's disability that violates their dignity or creates an intimidating, hostile, degrading, humiliating, or offensive environment.⁷⁵ Harassment can take many forms, including offensive jokes, slurs, or physical threats. The Act seeks to protect individuals from such degrading treatment, ensuring that all environments, particularly workplaces and educational institutions, are respectful and inclusive. Victimization occurs when an individual is treated unfairly because they have made or supported a complaint under the Equality Act 2010.⁷⁶

(c) Reasonable adjustments

The Equality Act 2010 establishes a vital framework for ensuring that individuals with disabilities are not unfairly disadvantaged in various aspects of life, including employment, education, and access to services. Central to this framework is the duty to make reasonable adjustments, as outlined in Sections 20 and 21 of the Act. This duty requires employers, service providers, and public authorities to take proactive steps to accommodate the needs of disabled individuals, thereby promoting inclusivity and equality.⁷⁷ The duty to make reasonable adjustments is designed to address and mitigate the barriers that disabled individuals may face. The adjustments are aimed at eliminating or reducing the disadvantages that disabled individuals encounter.

Reasonable adjustments can be broadly categorized into physical adjustments and adjustments to policies, procedures, or practices. Physical adjustments involve

⁷² Bell Mark, *Equality and anti-discrimination law: the Equality Act 2010 and other anti-discrimination protections*. Spiramus Press Ltd (2016).

⁷³ Section 19, Equality Act, 2010.

⁷⁴ Bell Mark, *op. cit.*

⁷⁵ Section 26, Equality Act, 2010.

⁷⁶ Section 27, Equality Act, 2010.

⁷⁷ Cameron Harriet, Bryan Coleman, Tamara Hervey, Sabrina Rahman, and Philip Rostant, 'Equality Law Obligations in Higher Education: reasonable adjustments under the Equality Act 2010 in assessment of students with unseen disabilities' *Legal Studies* (2019) 39(2), 204-229.

modifications to the physical environment to make it accessible to individuals with disabilities.⁷⁸ For instance, providing accessible facilities such as ramps, elevators, widened doorways, and accessible restrooms ensures that buildings are navigable for people with mobility impairments. Similarly, providing specialized equipment like screen readers for visually impaired individuals, hearing loops for those with hearing impairments, or ergonomic furniture for those with mobility issues can significantly enhance accessibility.⁷⁹

Adjustments to policies, procedures, or practices involve changing the way things are done to remove barriers for disabled individuals.⁸⁰ Flexible working arrangements, such as allowing remote work or flexible hours, can accommodate employees who might struggle with traditional schedules due to their disabilities.⁸¹ Modifying procedures, such as providing information in alternative formats like braille, large print, or audio versions, or offering additional assistance to navigate complex procedures, ensures that services are accessible to all. Additionally, training staff to understand and support the needs of disabled individuals fosters a more inclusive and supportive environment.⁸² Also, failure to make reasonable adjustments constitutes discrimination under the Equality Act 2010.⁸³ This form of discrimination occurs when an employer, service provider, or public authority neglects to take the necessary steps to accommodate a disabled individual.

(d) Discrimination arising from disability

Discrimination arising from disability has been outlawed through section 15 of the Equality Act 2010 UK this is because discrimination exists where an individual is easily treated unfairly by his employer or anyone else by reason of a circumstance arising from disability, not the disability as such. It is this paragraph that shields one from discrimination on account of the behaviors, conditions, or appearances associated with the impairment. It seeks to protect equal opportunity so that the intended adverse impact of disability conditions is dealt with whether it is in form of forcing disabled employees to attend often due to their disability or ejecting or punishing them due to behaviors caused by disability. The Act also provides for the justification of treatment when the latter is a proportional means to a legitimate end with Social Disability becoming admissible as a ground for removing discrimination of people with disabilities in employment, education or availability of essential services.⁸⁴

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ Section 20(4), Equality Act, 2010.

⁸⁰ Cameron Harriet, Bryan Coleman, Tamara Hervey, Sabrina Rahman, and Philip Rostant, *op. cit.*

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Section 20(3), Equality Act, 2010.

⁸³ Section 21, Equality Act, 2010.

⁸⁴ Section 15(1)(b), Equality Act, 2010.

(e) Public sector equality duty

The Public Sector Equality Duty, set out in Section 149 of the Equality Act 2010, is an absolute requirement with a 'public interest' function which is fundamental for promoting equality and reducing discrimination for disabled people and other vulnerable groups in the society. It requires the implementation of the interests of disabled persons in the operation of the said bodies, including policy-making and organizational, decision-making, and service provision. Thus, through promoting work and education for disabled people, governance for their rights, and equality, therefore receiving relevant reports, the PSED aims at making appropriate changes that would guarantee all disabled persons equal opportunities and the option to be active in all spheres of life.

7. STRENGTHS OF THE NIGERIAN DISABILITIES ACT, 2018

The Discrimination against Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 signifies a significant and commendable step by the Nigerian government towards guaranteeing the rights of people living with disabilities and protecting them against discrimination. The Act's broad application is one of its major strengths, as it prohibits discrimination across various domains, including access to public services, employment, healthcare, and education. This comprehensive approach ensures that individuals with disabilities are safeguarded from discrimination not just in one specific setting but throughout their entire lives, fostering an inclusive and equitable society.⁸⁵

The Act's provisions regarding employment practices are particularly noteworthy. By mandating that employers make reasonable accommodations for qualified candidates or workers with disabilities, the Act aims to level the playing field and create an environment where individuals with disabilities can thrive and contribute to their fullest potential.⁸⁶ This requirement recognizes that disabilities may necessitate certain modifications or adjustments in the workplace, and it places the onus on employers to facilitate these accommodations. Equally, through this Act, reasonable accommodations can take various forms, such as providing assistive technologies, modifying physical infrastructure to ensure accessibility, or offering flexible work arrangements.⁸⁷ These accommodations not only enable individuals with disabilities to perform their job duties effectively but also promote their overall well-being and job satisfaction.

Furthermore, the Act's prohibition of discrimination in educational settings is a crucial step towards ensuring equal opportunities for students with disabilities. By barring discrimination in admissions processes, access to facilities, and participation in

⁸⁵ Muhammad Mansur Aliyu, 'Rights of Persons Living with Disabilities under the Discrimination against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act 2018' *IJOCLLEP* (2019) 1, 112.

⁸⁶ *Ibid.*

⁸⁷ Arimoro Augustine Edobor, 'Nigeria's Legislation Against Discrimination of Persons With Disabilities: An Assessment' In *Social, Educational, and Cultural Perspectives of Disabilities in the Global South*, IGI Global (2021) 55-67.

programs, the Act aims to create an inclusive learning environment where students with disabilities can pursue their academic aspirations without facing unnecessary obstacles or prejudice.⁸⁸ In addition, any change or adjustment made to a job or work environment that enables a candidate or employee with a disability to participate in the application process or carry out necessary job functions is known as a reasonable accommodation.⁸⁹

Noteworthy, the Act gives the commission the ability to hear complaints about harmful practices, harassment, and discrimination, among other things.⁹⁰ The creation of these federal commissions is based on the need to have a body to address the problems disabled people face. Additionally, the Act gives accessibility measures a top priority. For people with disabilities, the Act eliminates physical barriers that have historically limited their participation by requiring changes to public buildings and transportation systems. More freedom and mobility are made possible by this accessibility-focused approach.

However, it is important to note that the successful implementation of the Act's provisions will require a concerted effort from various stakeholders, including the government, private sector, educational institutions, and civil society organizations. Adequate resources, infrastructure upgrades, awareness campaigns, and robust monitoring mechanisms will be essential to translate the Act's intentions into tangible outcomes. Additionally, addressing societal attitudes and misconceptions surrounding disability will be a critical component of the Act's long-term impact. In all, the Discrimination against Persons Living with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, 2018 represents a significant milestone in Nigeria's efforts to protect the rights of individuals with disabilities and promote an inclusive society.

8. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE NIGERIAN DISABILITIES ACT, 2018 AND THE UK EQUALITY ACT, 2010

The Nigerian Disability Act, 2018 and the UK Equality Act, 2010 share a fundamental commitment to protecting the rights of individuals with disabilities and promoting their integration into society. However, they diverge significantly in their provisions and approaches, reflecting distinct legal frameworks shaped by their respective societal contexts.

Notably, the Nigerian Disability Act defines disability broadly as "a long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairment which, in interaction with various barriers,

⁸⁸ Nwamaka Adaorah Iguh, and Maureen Obiageli Ugwu, 'Protecting and Promoting the Rights of Persons with Disability in Nigeria' *IRLJ* (2023) 5, 153.

⁸⁹ Ade Oba Raji, 'What Nigerian law says about treatment of people living with disabilities' *Pulse NG* (28 March 2024) <<https://www.pulse.ng/news/local/nigerian-law-treatment-of-people-with-disabilities/tv116ew>> accessed on 7 May 2024.

⁹⁰ Section 38, Discrimination against people living with disabilities Act, 2018.

may hinder the full and effective participation in society of a person on an equal basis with others."⁹¹ This expansive definition highlights the interaction between impairments and societal barriers, emphasizing the need to address environmental and social factors that hinder participation. In contrast, the UK Equality Act provides a more specific definition, focusing on the substantial and long-term adverse effect of an impairment on a person's ability to carry out normal day-to-day activities. This precise definition sets clear criteria for determining disability under the law, ensuring consistency in identifying individuals eligible for protection against discrimination.⁹²

Furthermore, under the Nigerian Disability Act, public and private entities are generally mandated to provide reasonable accommodations to individuals with disabilities.⁹³ However, the Act lacks detailed guidance or specific requirements on what constitutes reasonable accommodations, leaving interpretation and implementation somewhat open-ended. Conversely, the UK Equality Act establishes comprehensive provisions on the duty to make reasonable adjustments. It stipulates specific requirements for employers, service providers, and public authorities to make adjustments that would alleviate disadvantages faced by disabled individuals. The Act also outlines factors to consider when assessing the reasonableness of accommodations, promoting clarity and consistency in implementation.⁹⁴

In another strand, the Nigerian Disability Act establishes a National Commission for Persons with Disabilities tasked with overseeing implementation and enforcement. Despite this oversight body, the Act does not specify clear mechanisms for individuals to seek redress or remedies in cases of discrimination, potentially limiting effective enforcement. In contrast, the UK Equality Act outlines robust mechanisms for enforcement. Individuals can lodge discrimination claims with employment tribunals or county courts, supported by the oversight of the Equality and Human Rights Commission. The Act provides remedies such as compensation and injunctions, ensuring that discriminatory practices are effectively addressed and deterred.

It is also worthy of note that the Nigerian Disability Act does not explicitly include provisions for positive action measures or affirmative action programs to address disadvantages faced by individuals with disabilities.⁹⁵ This absence limits proactive efforts to promote equality and inclusivity through targeted interventions. Conversely, the UK Equality Act permits positive action measures. Employers and service providers can

⁹¹ Section 57, Disability Act, 2018.

⁹² Oluwafunmilola Ohunene Ogunsakin, *A Comparative Analysis of the Legal Regime for the Protection of the Rights of Disabled Persons in The UK and Nigeria* (Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin, Ilorin) (2021).

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ Adaora Nwamaka Iguh, Boniface Ebele Ewulum & Alphonsus Maduka Ewuzie 'Disability and the Law in Nigeria: An Analysis' *Special Needs Education from The Lens of Interdisciplinary Dialogue: A Festschrift in Honour of Prof. Emeka D. Ozoji*, (2023) 2(1).

implement targeted recruitment or support programs to overcome or minimize disadvantages experienced by disabled individuals. These measures facilitate greater inclusivity in workplaces and service provisions, fostering environments where disabled individuals can thrive.⁹⁶

In addition, the Nigerian Disability Act does not impose a specific duty on public authorities to consider the needs of individuals with disabilities in their decision-making processes and functions. This omission may hinder efforts to embed disability considerations into public policies and services systematically. In contrast, the UK Equality Act includes a robust Public Sector Equality Duty. This duty mandates that public authorities have due regard to the need to eliminate discrimination, advance equality of opportunity, and foster good relations between disabled and non-disabled individuals. It requires proactive steps to promote inclusivity and accessibility across public services, fostering a culture of equality and accountability.

Besides, the Nigerian Disability Act primarily focuses on improving accessibility, enhancing educational opportunities, ensuring healthcare access, and promoting employment for individuals with disabilities. However, it does not provide comprehensive coverage of critical areas such as access to goods and services, housing, or transportation, potentially leaving gaps in protection. In contrast, the UK Equality Act offers a broad scope of protection. It comprehensively covers various aspects of life, including employment, education, provision of goods and services, housing, and public functions.⁹⁷ While both the Nigerian Disability Act, 2018 and the UK Equality Act, 2010 aim to uphold the rights and inclusion of individuals with disabilities, they operate within distinct legal frameworks with varying provisions and scopes.

10. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE NIGERIAN ACT

i. Stronger and nationwide enforcement

The Act's effectiveness hinges on its ability to enforce its provisions. Strengthening the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities with adequate resources and personnel is crucial. Collaboration with relevant authorities, like state governments, can ensure nationwide enforcement.

ii. Refinement of definition

Nigeria should consider revising its definition of disability to adopt a more specific criterion akin to that in the UK Equality Act. This revision would provide clearer

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

guidelines for identifying individuals entitled to protection against discrimination and ensure consistency in legal interpretations.

iii. Improved awareness

The Act's target population – individuals with disabilities – are not aware of its provisions. It is imperative to distribute the Act in accessible formats such as audio recordings, Braille, and sign language. Collaboration between disability rights organizations and community outreach campaigns can guarantee that the message reaches its intended audience.

iv. Improved funding

Implementing the Act requires significant financial investment. Advocating for increased budgetary allocation towards the commission and disability initiatives is crucial. Additionally, exploring public-private partnerships can leverage additional resources for implementing accessibility measures.

v. Addressing diverse needs

Although the Act covers a wide range of disabilities, specialized assistance is still essential. The development of targeted support services and the distribution of resources will be influenced by the gathering of data on the unique requirements of various disability types. Ensuring the efficacy of these solutions can be achieved through collaborating with disability experts and organizations.

11. CONCLUSION

For Nigerians with disabilities, the Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act of 2018 is a major advancement in their rights. The all-encompassing approach of the Act forbids discrimination in all areas of life, requires accessibility measures, and encourages socio-economic inclusion. A central organization for advocacy and enforcement was established with the creation of the National Commission for Persons with Disabilities. The Act is not without flaws, though. There are issues with resource limitations, low public awareness, and enforcement methods. Furthermore, not all disability types' diverse needs may be fully addressed by the Act. Important actions include fortifying the Commission, promoting public awareness campaigns in easily comprehensible formats, and investigating funding opportunities through public-private partnerships.